

Investigation of fishing gears in Pyinbongyi Village, Bago Township, Bago Region

Khin Swe Wynn^{*}, Aye Aye Kyu^{**}, Nyein Nyein Moe^{***}, Kalayar Win Maung^{****},
Khin Htwe Win^{*****}

Abstract

Pyinbongyi village is located in Bago Township, Bago Region was chosen as the study area. It is situated at 16° 45' N, 95° 34' E and 25 km far from Northern East of Bago, East of the Yangon to Mandalay highway. The study was conducted from January 2018 to December 2018. Twenty eight species belonging to 22 genera and 16 families of 7 orders were recorded from the study area. Seventeen kinds of fishing gears recorded in the study area all year round.

Key words: Fishing gear, Species, Genera, Families, Orders

Introduction

Myanmar, with a coast of 2826 Km with many rivers flowing into the extended and large continental shelf of 213,720 km² with an Exclusive Economic Zone of 486000 km², is rich in natural fisheries resources. Inland freshwater bodies cover 8.1 million ha which 1.3 million ha are permanent, the remainder are seasonally inundated floodplain. Fishery is important to food security and poverty alleviation for the country. Moreover, small - scale fisheries play a crucial role as source of livelihood and income for millions for people in Myanmar (FAO, 1996).

Over the years, unsustainable fisheries practices have significantly impacted on the fish supply and the food security of the people. The fisheries products are primarily used for food, and the other uses are for animal feeds and fertilizers. Fishing gears used in inland fisheries are traditionally developed from small scale fishing activities. The most widely used gears include fish trap, upright fish trap, upright eel trap, man push net, plung basket, drop door trap, fish trap, cast net, net trap, drift gill net, set gill net, shallow bamboo stake trap, stationary bamboo trap, stationary bamboo fish filter in the study area (FAO,1996).

Fishing gears are quite selective and sample to use. Practically, Inland fisheries can fish all the year round but the amount of caught may vary from season to season. Fishery management requires a good knowledge of fishing gear. There is great divergence in the efficiency of different forms of fishing gear. Normally fisheries in the study area are small scales. Since the fisheries are the livelihood of the fishing villages in general, the villagers usually behave fishing in a sustainable manner. Fishers should keep their limit on their own in order to further enhancement of the stock in future. So the fishing gears are very important for the natural fisheries resources to restore and sustain (Brandt, 1984).

The present study was conducted at Pyinpongnyi village located in Bago Township. The present work was undertaken on the fishing gear within the selected study area with the following objectives:

- To determine the types of fishing gears used in the study area
- To categorize the fish species in the study area

* Dr., Professor / Head, Department of Zoology, Bago University

** Lecturer, Department of Zoology, Bago University

*** Lecturer, Department of Zoology, Bago University

**** Dr., Lecturer, Department of Zoology, Yangon University

***** Dr., Assistant Lecturer, Department of Zoology, Bago University

Materials and Methods

Study area

Pyinbongyi village is located in Bago Township, Bago Region was chosen as the study area. It is situated at 16° 45' N, 95° 34' E and 25 km far from Northern East of Bago, East of the Yangon to Mandalay highway (Fig.1). Moeyingyi Wildlife Sanctuary (Moeyingyi Wetland) lies in the North - East of Pyinbongyi village. It is one of the protected areas in Myanmar and the area is 100 square kilometer.

Study period

The study was conducted from January 2018 to December 2018.

Fish sample collection

Fish specimens were collected from the fishermen in study area. Scaled photographs were taken soon after catch to obtain the natural size and colour and labeled with local name before preserving them in 10% formalin for detailed identification. The fishing gears were recorded and took photograph.

Identification of fish species

Identification of fish species was followed after by Jayaram (1981), Talwarand Jhingran (1991), Rainboth (1996) and Ferraris Jr. (1997).

Recording of utilized fishing gears and methods

The fishing gears and methods utilized in the study area were recorded together with target fish species and identified according to Brandt (1984) and FAO (1990).

Figure (1) Map of study area

(Source: Google map)

Results

Seventeen kinds of fishing gears were recorded in the study area. They are Fish trap, Upright fish trap, Upright eel trap, Man push net, Fish trap(Yin kwemyone), Fish trap (Paing), Cast net, Fish trap (Sayikemyone), Net trap, Plung Basket, Upright fish trap, Fish trap, Eel trap, Bottom Set gill net, Stationary bamboo trap, Myhein and Kayar. (Plate I, II).Twenty eight fish species belonging to 22 genera and 16 families of 7 orders were recorded in the study area. (Table 1).

Ngalayhmyone

Upright fish trap

Upright eel trap (Ngazinyaingpone)

Man push net (Yin toon)

Stationary bamboo

Fish trap (Yin kwemyone)

Fish trap (Paing)

Fish trap (sayikehmyone)

Plung Basket (Ngaoaksaung)

Plate (I). Fishing gears utilized in the study area

Cast net (Let pyit kun)

Bottom set gill net (Tar pike)

Ngahtoesuu (Myhein)

Khayar

Net trap (Dine kwin)

Plate (II). Fishing gears utilized in the study area

Table. (1) Categorized fishing gears utilized in the study area

Sr No	Gear name	Local name	Target fish species
1	Fish trap	Nga lay myone	<i>Macroganathussp.</i> , <i>Puntius sophore</i> , <i>Mystus sp.</i> , <i>Amblypharyngodon mola</i> , <i>Parambassis ranga</i> , <i>Glossogobius giuris</i> , <i>Xenodon cancella</i> , <i>Colisalabiosa</i>
2	Upright fish trap	Ngazinyine pone	<i>Mystus sp.</i> , <i>Puntius sophore</i> , <i>Clarias batrachus</i> , <i>Channa sp.</i>
3	Upright eel trap	Ngashintmyone	<i>Ophisternon bengalense</i>
4	Man push net	Yin toon	<i>Channa sp.</i> , <i>Clarias batrachus</i> , <i>Heteropneustes fossilis</i> , shrimp
5	Fish trap	Yin kwemyone	<i>Puntius sophore</i> , <i>Amblypharyngodon mola</i> , <i>Mystus sp.</i> , <i>Colisalabiosa</i> , small shrimp
6	Fish trap	Paing	<i>Mystus sp.</i> , <i>Puntius sophore</i> , <i>Channa sp.</i> , <i>Clarias batrachus</i> , <i>Heteropneustes fossilis</i> , Pazunhtoke
7	Cast net	Latpyitkon	<i>Wallago attu</i> , <i>Channa striatus</i> , <i>Notopterus notopterus</i> , <i>Osteobrama belangeri</i> , <i>Mystus sp.</i> , <i>Clarias batrachus</i> , <i>Heteropneustes fossilis</i>
8	Fish trap	Sayikemyone	<i>Channa striatus</i> , <i>Channa punctatus</i> , <i>Clarias batrachus</i> , <i>Heteropneustes fossilis</i> , <i>Macroganathussp.</i> , <i>Glossogobius giuris</i> , <i>Notopterus notopterus</i> , <i>Osteobrama belangeri</i> ,
9	Net trap	Dine kwinn	<i>Channa striatus</i> , <i>Clarias batrachus</i> , <i>Heteropneustes fossilis</i> , <i>Wallago attu</i> , <i>Ompok bimaculatus</i>
10	Plung Basket	Nga oak saung	<i>Channa striatus</i>
11	Upright fish trap	Ngakhu pone	<i>Channa striatus</i> , <i>Clarias batrachus</i>
12	Fish trap	Ngamway toe myone	<i>Macroganathussp.</i> , <i>Macroganathus zebrinus</i>
13	Eel trap	Ngashint pone	<i>Monopterus bengalense</i>
14	Bottom Set gill net	Tar pike	<i>Wallago attu</i> , <i>Channa striatus</i> , <i>Clarias batrachus</i> , <i>Heteropneustes fossilis</i> , <i>Mystus sp.</i> , <i>Xenodon cancella</i> , <i>Barbonymus gonionotus</i>
15	Stationary bamboo trap	Wunn khan sae	<i>Anabas testudineus</i> , <i>Channa striatus</i> , <i>Clarias batrachus</i> , <i>Heteropneustes fossilis</i> , <i>Wallago attu</i> , <i>Ompok bimaculatus</i> , <i>Xenodon cancella</i> , <i>Macroganathussp.</i> , <i>Glossogobius giuris</i> , <i>Amblypharyngodon mola</i> , <i>Puntius sophore</i> , <i>Lepidocephalus berdmorei</i> , <i>Channa punctatus</i>
16	Myhein	Ngahtoesuu	<i>Wallago attu</i> , <i>Clarias batrachus</i> , <i>Heteropneustes fossilis</i> , <i>Channa striatus</i>
17	Kayar	Kayar	<i>Wallago attu</i> , <i>Clarias batrachus</i> , <i>Heteropneustes fossilis</i> , <i>Channa striatus</i>

Discussion

Myanmar has many kinds of fish species in inland and marine water. A total of 754 species that include 291 species in freshwater and 463 species in brackish as well as marine water is found in Myanmar (Fishbase, 1996). A total of twenty eight fish species were caught by seventeen kinds of fishing gears were recorded in the study area.

More fishing activities were found during dry season after water level was receded in dry season. All fishers were small scale fishers and used various types of fishing gears to catch fish for their families' consumption and income. In the study area, fishers caught aquatic animals by Fish trap, Upright fish trap, Upright eel trap, Man push net, Fish trap (Yinkwemyone), Fish trap (Paing), Cast net, Fish trap (Sayikemyone), Net trap, Plung Basket

, Upright fish trap, Fish trap, Eel trap , Bottom Set gill net, Stationary bamboo trap, Myhein and Kayar were used in all year round depending on water level.

These fishing gears are rather selective and simple for using. However, the use of fishing gears in the Inn waters has to be permitted by authorities according to the Freshwater Fisheries Law (1991). Practically, fisheries can fish all year round but the amount caught may differ from time to time. Freshwater fish is abundant during the rainy season from June to September. During this period rivers, wetlands and floodplains are very creative as new water stimulates spawning. Yearling fish will grow to full size during rainy season and are the goal of fishing effort. Following the rainy season (October to December) water level in most inland habitats start leveling off. This enables fishers to easily access grown fish from rainy season using various fishing gears. Fishing can be done all year round in rivers and inn but fish are caught more readily from (July to September) when the water level is low. Several of the recorded fishing gears and methods are legally in Myanmar.

There was many different freshwater fish species were distributed. Fish catch rate was declining year by year because fishers' population was gradually increasing. Aquatic population was assumed to be decreasing and threaten to aquatic biodiversity in the study area. The study indicated that community base management and educational programme for local people were needed to preserve aquatic biodiversity.

The fisheries area is very important in Myanmar's economy, as fish create a major source of animal protein in the food of the people. It also provides income generation to government and especially to the family economy of the rural people. The present study could not be requested to be complete but the recorded data in this work would certainly develop the information on fish fauna and fishing gears of Myanmar

Acknowledgements

We would like to express our profound gratitude to Dr Aye Aye Tun, Rector of Bago University and Dr Yin Yin Than, Pro-Rector of Bago University, who had encouraged and gave suggestions for this paper. We also thankful to U Sai Kyaw Myint , Director of Fishery Department of Bago Region, for his kind help in giving some data. Our thanks also go to the U Moe Kyaw, Administrator from Pyinbongyi Village, for his supporting data for this research. We also thanks goes to fishermen from Pyinbongyi Village, Bago Region, for their valuable information for this research.

References

- Brandt**, A.V. (1984) Fish catching methods of the world. Fishing. News Books Ltd. England.415 pp.
- Day**, F (1978) *The fishes of India being a natural history of the fishes known to inhabits the sea and freshwater of India, Burma and Ceylon*, Vol I & II (reprint 1958), Today & Tomorrow Book Agency, New Delhi.
- Ferraris Jr.**, C. J. (1997) Identification guide to the commercial inland fishes of central Myanmar. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. Myanmar: 58 pp.
- Food and Agriculture Organization** (FAO). (1990). Definition and classification of fishing gear categories. FAO fisheries technical paper. Rome. 88 pp.
- FAO** (1996).Regional compendium on aquaculture and inland fisheries legislation (Asian Region). FAO Development Law Service. Rome, FAO.
- Jayaran**, K. C. M. (1981). *The freshwater fishes India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Burma and Sri Lanka*. Edited by the Director, Zoological Survey of India, Calcutta.
- Rainboth**, W. J. (1996) Fishes of the Cambodian Mekong. Food and Agriculture Organization of the united Nations, Rome: 265 pp.
- Talwar**, P. K. and A. G. Jhingran. (1992). *Inland fishes of India and adjacent countries*. Vol I, Oxford & IBH Publishing Co Ltd, New Delhi, Bombay, Calutta.

<http://www.fishbase.org/Country/CountrySearchList.cfm?Country=104>